

Research Article

Evaluation of Organo-Mineral Fertilizer Application Rates for Optimum Yield of Upland Rice in Mokwa (Southern Guinea Savanna) Nigeria

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Abstract

The rate of application of organo-mineral fertilizer (cured cattle dung + urea N) required for optimum yield of upland rice (NERICA 8) in Mokwa (southern guinea savanna) was investigated in 2016 and 2017. The treatments consisted of nine organo-mineral fertilizer (OMF) application rates of 0, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1200, 1400, 1600 kg⁻¹ and mineral fertilizer applied at the rate of 40N-20P-20K. The treatments were imposed by broadcasting at two weeks after planting upland rice. The experimental design was a randomize complete block (RCB), replicated three times. Upland rice was planted on the flat at a spacing of 20 x 20cm. Results obtained indicated that optimum numbers of tillers and panicles/m² were obtained when OMF was applied at the rate of 200kg⁻¹ in both years. An optimum upland rice yield of 1,150 and 1,280 kg⁻¹ was also obtained when OMF was applied at the rate of 200kg⁻¹ in 2016 and 2017 respectively.

KEYWORDS: *Cured cattle dung, Urea, Organo-mineral fertilizer, Upland rice.*

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Introduction

Soils in the savanna are often deficient in Nitrogen (N), Phosphorous (P), Potassium (K), Organic matter (OM) and Cat-ion Exchange Capacity (CEC). Furthermore, the clay in these areas is Kaolinite, which is low activity clay (Sanchez and Jama, 2002). National Institute for Social and Economic Research (NISER, 2003) reported that Nigerian farmers have limited access to inorganic fertilizers because of low production, procurement and

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distribution. Furthermore, the use of inorganic fertilizer alone has been reported to have negative effects on the environment, such as nitrate leaching, ground water pollution, degradation of soil structure, decrease in soil pH and surface water infiltration (Ponded *et al.*, 2001).

The use of organo-mineral fertilizer to enhance soil fertility has been shown to be a better alternative to the use of mineral or organic fertilizer alone. Audu *et al.* (2015), reported that a screen house experiment was conducted to determine the influence of industrially formulated organo-mineral fertilizer (OMF) on some chemical properties of the soil and growth performance of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) in Sokoto, Sudan zone of Nigeria. Result obtained indicated that application of OMF at the rates of 130, 170, 210 and 250 kg/ha improved soil nutrient status, growth and yield of rice in Sudan savanna agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. Denize *et al.* (2017), evaluated three fertilizers with different sources of phosphorus (i.e. Triple Super Phosphate, OMF + Triple Super Phosphate, OMF + Bayover phosphate) at the rates of 0, 65, 130, 195, and 260 kg ha⁻¹. They found out that the three cultures assessed presented higher productivity when compared to the average of the factorial treatments that received phosphate fertilization relative to the control. They concluded that OMF increased grain production, obtaining average productivity equal to or greater than those obtained with the exclusive use of Triple Super Phosphate (STP). Ayeni (2012), reported that organic and organo-mineral fertilizer at low levels of application of about 2.5t/ha could be used to increase plant nutrients as well as maize production in south western Nigeria. Olowoake (2014), reported that organic fertilizers fortified with mineral fertilizers have great potentials in the production of *Amaranth* and could also be used effectively in increasing soil fertility for *amaranth* production. Omueti and Ogazi (2000) reported that organo-mineral fertilizer applied at the rate of 2.5t/ha equivalent to 90kg N/ha, 60kg P/ha and 40kg K/ha significantly increased maize yields in a maize/cassava intercrop by 60% compared with zero fertilizer application and 20% compared with the application of mineral fertilizer. OMF also gave the highest cassava tuber yield of 10.10t/ha, which was 200% higher than the control plots without fertilizers and 40% increase over mineral fertilizer. Eifediyi *et al.* (2013), reported that OMF applied at the rate of 3tons/ha enhanced the growth of Mallow (*Corchorous olitorius*) in Ilorin, Southern Guinea Savanna, Nigeria.

Sewage sludge is rich in phosphorus but low in nitrogen and potassium. Technology exists to supplement sewage sludge with mineral fertilizers such as urea and muraite of potash as sources of nitrogen and potassium respectively, to produce organo-mineral fertilizer with balance crop nutrient. Deeks *et al.* (2013), reported that a sludge based OMF that was enriched with N and K gave crop yields that were not significantly different

from the yields obtained when mineral fertilizer was used. Mercy and Omueti (2014), reported that OMF was effective in releasing phosphorus (P) for maize growth and building up P to moderate levels (13.4 to 14.8mg kg⁻¹) in P unresponsive soil. They further reported that the OMF contains sufficient concentration of exchangeable bases to bring about an increase in soil pH. Olowokere (2014), recommended that pepper can be grown with 100% organo-mineral fertilizer(OMF), OMF + chemical fertilizer(CF) [25 +75] %, OMF+ CF (75 +25)%, or OMF + CF [50% + 50%] for improved yield, growth, nutrient composition and soil quality. In Mokwa local government area of Niger state, cattle dung was available in sufficient quantity. Cattle dung was therefore cured and enriched with N from urea to produce organo-mineral fertilizer. The application rate of the OMF required for optimum yield of upland rice was evaluated in a field experiment at the National Cereals Research Institute (NCRI) experimental station at Mokwa. There is presently no information on the rate of application of OMF formulated from cured cattle dung + Urea (N) for optimum yield of upland rice in the Southern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. This experiment was therefore carried out to provide this information.

Materials and Methods

Cattle dung was cured in the months of March, April, May and part of June by moistening with water and stirring at weekly intervals. To the cured cattle dung was added nitrogen (N) from urea at the rate of 11.5kgN per 100kg of cured cattle dung. The mixture of cured cattle dung and N from urea was thoroughly mixed to form the cattle dung based organo-mineral fertilizer (OMF). The rate of application of the OMF required for optimum yield of upland rice was then evaluated in a field experiment during the 2016 and 2017 cropping seasons. The carbon to nitrogen C: N ratio, N P K, cat-ion, organic carbon and organic matter content of the OMF were determined. Composite soil samples were also obtained from the experimental site before planting for the determination of physical and chemical properties of the soil. Upland rice was planted on the 20th of June in both years.

Ten treatments, which consisted of nine OMF application rates of 0, 200, 400, 600, 800, 1000, 1200, 1400 and 1600kg⁻¹ and mineral fertilizer applied at the rate of 40N-20P-20K were applied to upland rice by broadcasting at 2Weeks After Planting. Except for the zero treatment which stands for the control, all the other OMF and mineral fertilizer treatments were side dressed with urea at the rate of 20kg⁻¹ N at upland rice booting stage. The experimental design was a randomized complete block (RCB) replicated three times. The gross plot size was 3 x 4m while the net plot size was 1 x 1m. Weed control was achieved by hoe weeding at 2, 4, and 6 weeks after planting. Data obtained includes upland rice plant height, numbers of tillers and panicles per plant and grain

yields. Data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis and significant means were separated by the new Duncan’s Multiple Range Test.

Result and Discussion

Upland rice plant heights were not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) at all the OMF application rates evaluated in both years. Optimum number of tillers/m² of 177.00 and 169.00 in 2016 and 2017 respectively, were obtained when OMF was applied at the rate of 200kg⁻¹. These tiller numbers were not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from those obtained when fertilizer was applied at the rate of 40N-20P-20K (i.e. 164 & 170) in both years (Tables 3 & 4). Optimum number of panicles/m² of 155 and 162 in 2016 and 2017 respectively, were obtained when OMF was applied at the rate of 200kg⁻¹. These numbers of panicles/m² were not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from those obtained when

Table 1: Soil test result of composite soil sample obtained before the application of organo-mineral fertilizer

Soil properties	2016	2017	Average
pH (H ₂ O)	5.83	5.74	5.790
Organic Carbon (g/Kg)	1.58	1.50	1.540
Total N (g/Kg)	0.04	0.03	0.035
Available P(mg/Kg)	2.62	2.58	2.600
<i>Exchangeable cat-ion</i>			
Ca(cmolKg/ha)	4.40	4.20	4.300
Mg(“)	2.75	2.70	2.730
K(“)	0.13	0.13	0.130
Na(“)	0.48	0.42	0.450
<i>Total acidity</i>	0.36	0.32	0.340
ECEC	8.12	7.77	7.950
Sand	89.68	89.68	89.680
Silt	8.56	7.84	8.200
Clay	1.76	1.48	1.620
Textural Class	Sandy		Sandy

Table 2: Laboratory analysis report of organo-mineral fertilizer

Chemical properties	Organomineral fertilizer
pH	6.89
C : N	6 : 1
Organic carbon %	24.82
Organic matter “	42.79
Nitrogen “	4.27
Phosphorus	1.10
Calcium	0.63
Potassium	1.07
Magnesium	0.54

Table 3: Upland rice growth parameters yield components and yields (2016)

Treatments -----Kg ⁻¹ -----	Plant Heights -----cm-----	Number of Tillers/m ²	Number of Panicles/m ²	Grain Yields Kg ⁻¹
-	-			
0	68.33	114.00ab	82.00b	670.00b
200	82.20	177.00a	155.00a	1150.00a
400	73.46	154.00a	128.00a	846.60ab
600	75.80	85.00b	80.00b	840.00ab
800	65.35	119.00a	75.00b	425.00c
1000	78.80	161.00a	138.00a	760.00b
1200	63.66	115.00a	86.00b	410.00c
1400	77.86	178.00a	129.00a	983.30a
1600	76.46	69.00b	61.00b	426.60c
40-20-20	79.33	164.00a	114.00ab	1220.00a
	N.S.			

Table 4: Upland rice growth parameters yield components and yields (2017)

Treatments -----Kg ⁻¹ -----	Plant Heights -----cm-----	Number of tillers/m ²	Number of panicle/m ²	Grain Yields Kg ⁻¹
0	65.88	64.00b	78.00b	480.00c
200	86.17	169.00c	162.00a	1280.00a
400	80.82	163.00a	154.00a	899.00ab
600	78.69	159.00a	156.00a	863.00ab
800	70.82	153.00a	150.00a	847.00ab
1000	77.67	167.00a	148.00a	833.00ab
1200	69.93	162.00a	142.00a	829.00ab
1400	84.37	171.00a	116.00ab	750.00b
1600	79.12	69.00b	112.00ab	738.00b
40-20-20	81.84	170.00a	159.00a	1269.00a
N.S.				

mineral fertilizer was applied at the rate of 40N-20P-20K (i.e.114 & 159) in both years. An optimum upland rice yield of 1,150 and 1,280 kg/ha in 2016 and 2017 respectively, were obtained when OMF was applied at the rate of 200kg/ha. These grain yields were not significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$) from those obtained when mineral fertilizer was applied at the rate of 40N-20P-20K (i.e. 1220 & 1269kg⁻¹) in both years.

The result obtained corroborates the findings by Audu *et al.* (2015), who reported that industrial formulated OMF applied at the rates of 130, 170, 210, and 250 kg⁻¹ improved soil nutrient status, growth and yield of rice in Sudan savanna agro-ecological zone of Nigeria. It also agrees with the work of Omueti and Ogazi (2000), who reported that OMF applied at the rate of 90kg N/ha, 60kg P/ha and 40kg K/ha significantly increased maize and cassava yields in maize/cassava intercrop. The improvement in crop performance as result of application of OMF in the works reported above was due to the organic matter (OM) added to the mineral fertilizer to produce the OMF. The OM improved the physical properties of the soil, enhanced the availability of cat-ions (i.e. Ca, Mg and k) which in turn caused the increase of the soil pH from the acid range to the neutral range. The increase of the soil pH to the neutral range enhanced the availability of macro and micro-nutrients to the upland rice.

Conclusion

Apply organo-mineral fertilizer (cured cattle dung + urea) at the rate of 200kg⁻¹ at two weeks after planting and side dress with urea at the rate of 20kg/ha N at booting to upland rice for optimum yield in the southern guinea savanna, Nigeria.

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